

A Preliminary Analysis of Post Types of Online Course Discussion

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ABSTRACT

We present a preliminary analysis of post types of asynchronous discussions in an online graduate course of Information and Library Science (ILS). Content analysis rendered a taxonomy with seven types, namely (1) reflecting on readings or lectures, (2) relating to personal experiences, (3) stimulating further discussions, (4) relating to real-life situations, (5) pointing to additional resources, (6) seeking answers, clarifications, or help, and (7) critiquing readings or lectures. The usefulness of the taxonomy is corroborated by a high inter-annotator agreement. The number of posts responding to the initial post of a thread, which can be regarded as an indicator of the popularity of the thread, is correlated to the initial post's type. The usefulness of the dataset produced from this line of research is discussed and future work is outlined.

KEYWORDS

discussion categorization; content analysis; learning management system

INTRODUCTION

Online discussion forums have become an integral part of many Learning Management Systems (LMS), such as Blackboard. As a computer-supported collaborative learning (CSCL) environment, online discussion forums make it possible for students to discuss course topics, share ideas and resources, interact and network with each other, and search and browse discussion content virtually anywhere and anytime; instructors also use them to monitor student participation and contribution, provide interventions and responses, and assess student learning outcomes. However, current LMS' support for these functions, as exemplified by the Blackboard system that our university uses, has a large room of improvement. Specifically, they do not provide a concise and accurate summary of the subject matter of each discussion post or thread, they do not provide information of the nature or type of each post or thread, and searches in this information space are limited to strict string matching. These issues become even more serious when the class size is large and when we want to reuse the discussion data for future classes. Thus, we identified the long-term goal of our research in this area is to develop online discussion forum tools that can automatically identify and suggest the topic, type, quality, difficulty level, and sentiment of each discussion post, thread, and forum based on historical data and user profiling; perform more sophisticated retrieval of information that goes beyond simple keyword matching; and generate various summative data that the instructor can use to assess individual students' participation, contribution, and learning outcomes. We believe the use of such tools can contribute to the improvement of online learning and instruction in various settings, including undergraduate and graduate programs.

We report here a preliminary study as the first step of our effort to develop such tools. Discussion board data of a core course in our Master of Library and Information Science (ILS) program are collected and analyzed. Several types (or categories) of discussion emerged from this analysis. We looked at the correlation between the type of the initial post of a thread and the activeness of students' participation in the thread. While much previous work has been done, including those looking into cognitive learning, information exchange, online communication and interaction, post quality, and post classification, the main contributions of our work include the development of a taxonomy to categorize discussion posts for courses in the ILS discipline and the demonstration of the correlation between the post type and other's interest in responding to it.

RELATED WORK

In the field of education, the studies of online discussion have mainly focused on the impact of online discussion participation on student course performance. Most of these studies use quantitative information such as message frequencies (the number of initiations and replies, the number of messages read, thread lengths, and response time from previous messages) to correlate them with course grades by stepwise multivariate linear regression analysis (Palmer et al., 2008), or use the number of posts and the number of page views to find relations between forum participation and course performance (Cheng et al., 2011); or model student activity using the number of messages written and read on the forum by students (Cobo et al., 2011). Another strand of research explore how discourse on discussion boards facilitates the construction of knowledge using qualitative method. De Wever et al (2006) indicated that a large number of instruments used for content analysis in computer-supported collaborative learning have a weak theoretical and empirical basis. They also noted the lack of replication studies that may strengthen the quality of existing content analysis instruments. Social Network Analysis (SNA) is the new trend in investigating the participation in online discussion. Zhang and Zhang (2010) used SNA to diagnose gaps in problem solving and knowledge construction. Their findings highlighted problems such as students with low levels of interaction and the

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presence of few central students to the exchange of information. Saqr et al (2018) used SNA to monitor collaborative groups and create a data-driven intervention that results in a meaningful improvement in the way students collaborate. Smith (2019) identified five main purposes of online discussion in a graduate course for students pursuing an initial teaching credential.

While online discussions have been widely studied in many disciplines or domains, in particular online shopping and product reviews (e.g., Pitta & Fowler, 2005), health informatics (e.g., Cole et al, 2016), education (e.g., Rovai, 2006), and social media (e.g., Ansari & Khan, 2020), research on the use of online discussion forums specifically in the ILS field is quite limited. Stansberry (2006) studied the effective assessment of online discourse in LIS education through analyzing student knowledge construction and learning with regard to the type of instructor's questions and the nature of student interaction. Using a survey and an online questionnaire, Airen (2015) identified main factors that determined the use of online discussion forums by postgraduate students in a Library and Information Science program in Nigeria. These factors include computer self-efficacy, perceptions of external control, computer anxiety, and computer playfulness. Rempel and McMillien (2008) used the discussion forum of Blackboard to engage distant students in workshops offered by the libraries at Oregon State University and received positive feedback from the participants. That study, however, focused on promoting library services to patrons. Redmond et al (2014) compared online discussions of engineering students and education students and found that the disciplinary differences led to different exhibitions of levels of thinking, frequencies of postings, and lengths of posts. According to teach.com, there are currently 40 institutions in the United States that offer online Master of Library and Information Science programs, 28 of which are accredited by the American Library Association (ALA). Therefore, it is of great importance for researchers to look specifically into the use of online discussion forums in our discipline and compare that with other disciplines. This is the motivation behind our research reported here

RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND METHODOLOGY

For the work reported in this paper, we are particularly interested in the following two questions:

1. Can we develop a taxonomy to categorize discussion posts in LIS courses, in particular those that initiate discussion threads?
2. Is students' interest in a thread, as measured by the total number of posts it contains, correlated to the type of its initial post? In other words, can we expect certain types of threads to attract more discussions than others?

For the first question, we chose to perform manual content analysis of a small sample of the dataset so that a tentative taxonomy of post types could be developed. We then applied this taxonomy to categorize the remaining posts in the dataset. Discussion posts are free text written by individual students on various aspects of online courses. The content analysis methodology is a natural choice for analyzing this kind of texts in order to reveal the underlying themes or categories (Krippendorff, 2015). Due to the relatively short length of each post, the general analysis guideline in our study is described as "using a phrase or a sentence to describe what the post is about." Once we accumulate sufficient brief descriptions of discussion posts, we can begin to develop categories based on them. The categories can then be used to classify future posts either manually or ultimately automatically. It should be noted that our focus in this study was on categorizing posts that started the discussion threads, which we called "initial posts." It should be noted that we use the word type and the word category interchangeably in this context. Additionally, we use Cohen's Kappa to measure the agreement of the categorization results of sample posts between the two researchers, which can demonstrate the reliability of the use of our taxonomy.

To answer the second question, we use one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to find out if there was any statistically significant difference on the number of posts contained in threads of different types. In this case, the category that the initial post of a thread falls into is the independent variable while the number of posts contained in the thread is the dependent variable. We assume that the population under each category follows a normal distribution, i.e., the number of posts contained in each thread in the given category. Our null hypothesis is that there is no statistically significant difference between these categories in terms of the average number of posts per thread of each category. While the rejection of the null hypothesis would not tell us what exactly caused the observed difference, it would suggest an area that deserves further investigation, e.g., through an interview with students to find out why they prefer to participate in certain categories of threads to others.

DATA PROCESSING AND ANNOTATION

The course we selected is a required course on the subject of information life cycle for our graduate ILS program. Specifically, we used the discussion board data generated in a section of this course offered in the fall semester in 2020. The class had about 35 students who were mostly in their first semester in the program. For each week, a discussion forum was created by the instructor on the discussion board of the Blackboard system; an additional forum was also created for students to ask questions for the instructor to answer. Within a forum, a student was free to create a new thread by submitting an initial post and/or participate in the discussion in any existing thread by

submitting a responding post. Each student was required at minimum for each week to create a new thread and respond to an existing thread. The scope of discussion was broadly instructed to include reflections on the week's topics, questions, comments, clarifications, pointers to useful resources, and responses to peers' posts. In total there were 14 discussion forums, 317 threads, and 1,002 posts for this course.

We started our analysis of initial post types with Week 1 discussion forum. Along the way new types were tentatively created and added to the taxonomy. The taxonomy was finalized after we analyzed about 50 threads. The taxonomy was then used in our annotation of the remaining threads.

PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS

In this section, we introduce a taxonomy of post types and the correlation between these types and thread popularity.

A taxonomy of post types

The taxonomy that we developed through our content analysis of the initial posts contained in the dataset includes seven categories, with at least five threads falling into each of them. The distributions of posts and threads in each category are shown in Table 1. We define these categories as: (1) *Reflecting on readings or lectures*. Each post in this category should discuss directly a topic mentioned either in a lecture or a required or optional reading, i.e., it must explicitly reference to the lecture slide(s) or the article where the topic is discussed. Posts that summarize a reading or readings also fall into this category; (2) *Relating to personal experiences*. Each post in this category must relate to the author's personal experience on the topic being discussed. For example, a post talking about how the author organizes her albums of family photos would belong to this category; (3) *Stimulating further discussions*. This category is for posts that explicitly solicit peers' opinions or thoughts on the topic being discussed. Posts in this category often contain expressions like "what do you think about it?" or "I wonder if any of you see it that way;" (4) *Relating to real-life situations*. Posts of this type talk about real life situations that are relevant to the topic being discussed though they do not need to be the author's personal experience. For example, a post like "the public library in my community has a librarian who has multiple responsibilities that should really be assigned to several librarians, but they do not have a choice due to the budget limit" is about a real-life situation but not about the poster's personal experience. Of course, there are posts that belong to both this type and Type 2 above; (5) *Pointing to additional resources*. Posts in this nature share relevant resources with classmates; they must contain references, pointers, or URLs to the resources being shared; (6) *Seeking answers, clarifications, or help*. Posts in this category must indicate the poster runs into questions, problems, difficulties, or confusions that need answers, clarifications, or help from peers or the instructor; and (7) *Critiquing readings or lectures*. Posts falling into this category must provide opinions, thoughts, explanations, etc. that are different from what's said in the readings or lectures; posts simply expressing agreements do not belong here - this is also how this category is differentiated from Category 1.

The annotations of the 317 initial posts contained in the dataset were completed by one of the two authors. As part of our ongoing work to label all posts by both researchers, we computed the inter-annotator agreement with categorization results of Week 2's discussion forum, which is what we have completed annotating at the time of this paper. Based on categorizations of 93 posts on this forum by each researcher, a Cohen's Kappa of 0.73 was achieved. Therefore, the agreement between the two researchers is substantial. It should be noted that two annotations of a given post are treated as an agreement only if they are identical. For example, if Annotator A labels a post as Type 2 and 3 while Annotator B labels it Type 2 only or Type 3 only, they are treated as a disagreement.

Correlation between thread type and thread popularity

Table 1 shows the total number of posts contained in threads that have the initial post of each type as well as the average number of posts per thread in each category. Specifically, about 60% of the initial posts fall into the category of reflecting on readings or lectures, which is the most commonly seen among the seven categories. In this type of posts, students mainly described their understandings of a topic or topics covered in the assigned reading or the weekly lecture. Posts in Category 2 (relating to personal experiences) are the second most. This is not surprising as many of our students are part-time students who also have a LIS-related job. Category 6 (Seeking answers, clarifications, or help) has the second fewest posts, possibly because of the existence of a dedicated forums of "Questions for the Instructors," which is not included in our analysis here. Finally, it is interesting to see that very few posts provided rebuttals or contradictory opinions against those in the assigned readings or the lectures, the reasons of which clearly deserve further investigations.

The average number of posts contained in a thread of each type is an indicator of how much participation of discussion it leads to, which is important for the purpose of online discussion forums. Looking at this column in Table 1, we find that threads of Type 3, 4, and 6 tend to have more posts (i.e., more posts responding to the initial post) than threads of other four types. We ran a one-way ANOVA to determine whether there are any statistically significant differences between the means of the number of posts in different categories. It turned out that the F value is 2.81 and the p value is 0.01, indicating statistically significant differences. Furthermore, a post hoc test

showed that threads in Category 6 (Seeking answers, clarifications, or help) contained significantly more posts than those in Category 7 (critiquing readings or lectures) and those in Category 2 (relating to personal experience).

Initial Post Type	Total Number of Threads	Total Number of Posts	Average Number of Posts per Thread
Reflecting on readings or lectures	201	605	3.0
Relating to personal experiences	59	163	2.8
Stimulating further discussions	34	150	4.4
Relating to real-life situations	25	104	4.2
Pointing to additional resources	10	35	3.5
Seeking answers, clarifications, or help	9	47	5.2
Critiquing readings or lectures	5	14	2.8

Table 1. Distribution of threads and the number of posts by the initial post's type

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

We reported our preliminary work on categorizing and analyzing the online course discussions. The dataset used in this study was collected from the discussion board of a required course on information life cycle in our MS in ILS program curriculum. Through content analysis, we developed a taxonomy of categories or types of posts that initiated discussion threads. These categories include Reflecting on readings or lectures, Relating to personal experiences, Stimulating further discussions, Relating to real-life situations, Pointing to additional resources, Seeking answers, clarifications, or help, and Critiquing readings. The dataset shows that more than 60% of the initial posts were students' reflections on the weekly readings or lectures. We found that initial posts that relate to real-life situations or stimulate further discussion tend to lead to more discussions within their threads, as measured by the total number of posts contained in each thread.

Although much remains to be done, our preliminary work as reported here has several main contributions. Firstly, it marks the first effort on building a dataset in the field of ILS that can be used to study the use of online discussion forums for learning, instruction, interaction, communication, and information search, access, and visualization. Secondly, we developed a taxonomy that can be used to categorize posts and threads on online course discussion forums. The categorization has the potential benefit of helping users search and access information of their interest more effectively and efficiently and assisting the instructor to evaluating each individual student's participation in and contribution to the discussion. Lastly, we revealed that the popularity of a discussion thread, as measured by the number of posts it contains, is correlated to the type of its initial post.

There are at least two limitations of this preliminary study. The dataset is from only one course and hence the question remains open-ended how well the taxonomy developed from this study can be used to accurately and adequately categorize discussions in other courses. Also, the research conducted for this paper did not involve any students from that class. It would be interesting and important to conduct interviews or surveys with students in order to find out their motivations for online discussion and their comments on the taxonomy. In addition to addressing these limitations, our future work will include annotating the difficulty level, quality, and sentiment of each post. Once this work is completed, conducting broader and in-depth data analyses including individual student's participations, contributions, and learning outcome achievements, and exploring the use of the state-of-the-art techniques of machine learning and information retrieval with the annotated data to improve the discussion features and functions so that it can better support online discussion among students and the instructor, searching for discussions of interest, as well as learning and instruction assessment.

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